

Introduction

While measuring longitudinal QoE is more time-consuming, it is crucial to understanding users' behavior when interacting with the service. Making decisions such as unsubscribing from a service or changing Internet providers are not done after a single interaction. They are part of a process that is not based on one quality judgment but on the memory of multiple experiences. My PhD is part of the international project "Towards Better Understanding of Factors Influencing the QoE by More Ecologically Valid Evaluation Standards" (TUFIQoE). Our goal is to better understand the process of interacting with a video service. This can be done by operationalizing the factors that influence QoE and increasing the ecological validity of subjective studies. In the project, I am responsible for the Long-Term Study, and the goal of my PhD is to investigate and better understand how people are affected by quality changes over a longer period of time. For the purposes of the study, we designed an application in which testers watch only one video per day for an extended period of time. Naturally, conducting such studies is much more time-consuming than traditional QoE studies, as they require longer collaboration with the testers. Data analysis is also quite challenging, as the testers who are asked to watch one video per day can produce more missing data than testers in a typical QoE experiment.

Traditional experiments in the laboratory are not close to realistic scenarios (new device, being observed, content) - solution: **living lab**

In real life we interact with service for long time, we build expectations and habits - solution: **longitudinal approach**

Study design

Methodology

In our Long-Term Study, the testers are using our mobile application. We observe the testers watching videos on their mobile phones when the testing environment is not controlled. Each of the testers has our mobile phone application installed on their phone. The app sends a daily notification about the video (the hour of notification is adjusted by the user) and allows the user to send feedback if there are issues within the application. The study is divided into six phases, each focused on a different research problem.

Number of participants: 38

Duration: > 1 year

Task: watch video in the app daily

Timeline of the study

Conclusions

In conclusion, we believe that our study design fills a gap in the current way QoE studies are conducted. The longitudinal study we propose allows us to simulate real-life interactions with the service. We developed and tested a mobile application that our testers have used for the past couple of months, and we are currently gathering data for the next part of the experiment.

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